

Research Article

FOLMOESUN: The Foldable Mobile Solar Dryer

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Abstract: Observing the decreasing amount of food source over the years combined with the rising food demand due to increasing population, it is of utmost importance for the masses to seek ways to preserve and improve food storing methods. As dehydrating foods has been one of the more primordial methods of food conservation, the team seeks to innovate a better dehydrator for home use. FOLMOESUN is a variation of the earlier MOESUN that provides convenience for homeowners and small businesses to dehydrate food through the portable solar dryer. A compact solar dryer, this innovative design is space saving due to its foldable nature and easy maneuverable within the homeowner's yard. It can be set to face the Sun movement throughout the day to provide optimal food dehydration. FOLMOESUN can be considered as a solar oven with a primary function as a dehydrator. As FOLMOESUN is fully covered by polycarbonate-based material, this dryer provides a more hygienic alternative to the regular open sun drying method. Once FOLMOESUN is constructed, the mobile solar dryer is tested to seek its effectiveness by observing the temperature changes within the dryer. It is observed that FOLMOESUN retains the same capability as its parent design, MOESUN, through maximum temperature difference of 20 degrees Celsius. FOLMOESUN does have the same potential to commercialize based on the data obtained. Costing details will be one of the steps needed to be taken to commercialize this product later on.

Keywords: solar dryer, heat retention, portable

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1. INTRODUCTION

Political and social conflicts, socio-economic conditions, natural hazards, climate change, and pests became one of the few factors that has caused an increase in chronic and acute hunger due to the disruption in food supply chain (Su, Wu, and Tan, 2023; Aday, 2020; World Bank, 2021). Even with these factors contributing to the rising food hunger and scarcity globally, the sudden pandemic that hit worldwide in 2020 has also affect food security. Despite the shift towards endemic, food security

problems will continue to rise over the next few years due to the rising irreversible climate change and population. It is imminent to seek methods of improving shelf life of harvest cropped to improve food security. An estimate of at least 40 to 50 percent post-harvest losses in developing countries occur due to the easily perishable nature of the crops and the inability to preserve crops before degradation (Wakholi, 2015).

One of the most common methods of food preservation is the open drying process. A study by Agbede et al and Groot et al discusses on how there are an abundant of fruit production during harvest season but lacks in useful shelf life which gives the stakeholders in the agroindustry to utilize different preservation method to minimize storage losses (Agbede, 2023; Groot, 2021). This preservation method uses direct solar exposure to remove moisture content from the products. By dehydrating these crops, produce can be kept longer, and food wastes can be avoided in the long run. While this method is economical on a large scale due to it cheaper operating costs as compared to an electrical dehydrator, this method poses problems as in it freely exposed to the unpredictable weather, animal attacks, dusts, and fungi. Not only that, but the unpredictable weather would also affect the moisture removal rate from the products as heat is not maintained as it lacks the enclosure.

An electrical dryer may solve this problem as heat is circulated within an enclosed space, however, electricity consumed by the dehydrator would become additional costs which will be incurred in the final product price. With the enclosed drying area or more commonly called as the solar dryer, dried products are less exposed animal attacks, pests, and dusts, making them more hygienic by lacking food contamination and has better quality, flavorful nutrient-dense food (Abideen, 2019). These solar dryers are more focused on its drying times, high higher efficiency, improved hygiene, healthier end products and are more cost effective as discussed by Fernandes and Tavares (Fernandes and Tavares, 2024).

It was even suggested that a forced convection solar dryer provides a better control on the required drying air conditions as compared to natural convection solar dryer which does not require any other energy during operation (Pangavhane, 2002). However, the team focuses on studies to seek a more portable design to the previous MOESUN (Halidi et al, 2023) created for the natural convection solar dryer. While MOESUN proved to be more economical than forced convection solar dryer, this product is still limited to its portability despite being designed with wheels. The team envisioned a smaller solar dryer which would be foldable that it can be brought anywhere to be used. This would attract a target of campers or mobile homes that require less space to keep the dryer when travelling. An optimally designed product would give a better utilization and efficiency to the solar dryer. Previous studies (Mustayen, 2014; Zheng, 2017) showed parameters such as sample thickness and drying tray material are just as important to the performance of the solar dehydrators. Not only that, but there were also previous papers that studied wall color and profile effects on the effectiveness of a solar dehydrator (Katunsky, 2022; Halidi, 2022). The factors were taken into consideration when designing the FOLMOESUN, the foldable version of the previous MOESUN.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

A foldable solar dryer, by its brand name, FOLMOESUN, is constructed for the study. The solar dryer frame is made of wood, riveted to aluminium sheets on its sides, except for the front and top. Not only that, but the sides are also hinged so that it can be folded when not in use. The design is as shown in Figure 1. The dryer is placed on an open area, not to be obstructed by the trees and building and in the lines of sunset and sunrise to obtain maximum solar exposure. The dehydrator is left for a maximum of 8 hours a day and to be observed hourly for its temperature reading. Data is also taken during cloudy windy weather to seek whether the dryer works during a less hot weather. The effectiveness of the

foldable mobile solar dryer is measured through temperature difference and the amount of moisture loss that can be obtained during a specific period. A high temperature difference would indicate sunlight is able to penetrate through the walls of the dehydrator and focus the heat on it.

Figure 1. a) CAD representation of FOLMOESUN; b) FOLMOESUN structure; c) FOLMOESUN collapsible feature

3. FINDINGS

Table 1 shows the maximum temperature difference obtained for the FOLMOESUN when being placed in an open area for 7 consecutive days. Figure 2 provides the graphical representation of the data in Table 1.

Table 1. Maximum Temperature Difference for FOLMOESUN.

Day	Average Ambient Surrounding Temperature (°C)	Maximum Temperature Obtained (°C)	Maximum Temperature Difference (°C)
1	32	52.9	20.9
2	31	41.4	10.5
3	31	44.7	13.7
4	29	40.9	11.9
5	30	35.9	5.9
6	26	47.0	21.0
7	30	39.6	9.6

Figure 2. Graphical Representation of Maximum Temperature Difference for FOLMOESUN

4. DISCUSSION

The graph shown in Figure 2 provides a graphical representation of the maximum temperature difference obtained for the FOLMOESUN for 7 consecutive days. Table 1 provides the average surrounding temperature, maximum temperature in the dryer and the maximum temperature difference daily. The maximum temperature obtained daily is highly dependable on the daily weather. Day 6 recorded the highest temperature gap with a difference of 21 degrees Celsius followed by day 1 at 20.9 degrees Celsius with a mere difference of 0.1 degrees. While day 6 has a lower averaged surrounding temperature compared to day 1 due to the rainy weather in the afternoon, both day 1 and day 6 had a sunny weather during the peak sun hours between 10AM and 4PM which provided enough heat in the FOLMOESUN to retain throughout the day. This correlated with studies done by the EPA where radiation is strongest during peak sun rays which are usually between 10AM and 4PM and meteorological studies that supported the average peak sun hours for Malaysia is between 4.0 to 5.5 hours a day (during the hottest part of the day) depending on the location within Malaysia (EPA, 2024; Top Solar, 2024).

Day 5 showed a huge drop in temperature difference which was 5.9 degrees Celsius. This is due to the weather on day 5 where it was cloudy for the whole day. The lack of sunlight exposure causes the inability for the dryer to conduct and radiate heat which then retain it within the dryer. This should not be treated as a disadvantage to the dryer as the FOLMOESUN can retain enough heat if there were enough sunlight during the peak sun hours as mentioned earlier. Even with lacking sunlight, the FOLMOESUN can still be used to dry any food but on a much slower rate than it was there is full sunlight exposure.

The materials used to construct the FOLMOESUN proves to be just as capable as its parent design which is the MOESUN. While FOLMOESUN uses aluminium for majority of its walls unlike the MOESUN which uses polycarbonate sheets all over the walls of the dryer, the heat conducting capability of aluminium sheets combined with polycarbonate sheet on two of FOLMOESUN walls proved to be just as efficient as MOESUN. Heat was conducted and radiated and focused into drying the product for both dryers.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the arguments provided, it can be concluded that the FOLMOESUN has the capability like its parent design, the MOESUN but offers a much more portability than its predecessor. Potential

users may need to adjust their drying time accordingly to achieve needed moisture loss specified by the users. It must also be emphasized that weather also plays a contributing role to the dryer. During rainy season, users of FOLMOESUN may opt to add on a fan to further expedite the drying process in the mobile solar dehydrator. However, this would come as additional costs and a need for a different design construction which must be included in any clients' consideration for FOLMOESUN. Further study can be conducted as such to include a more fluid design for the FOLMOESUN to accommodate various clients' needs with added features that can further improve the dryer when used during cloudy weather.

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